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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 5.14. Compendium of scientific publications (year 2)

Version 1

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0.1	September 30, 2023	Mafalda Casais (ISCTE-IUL)
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Executive summary

This is a report of the publications made by early-stage researchers between October 2022 and September 2023.

A total of 31 scientific contributions, including conference abstracts, presentations and papers, and journal articles, have been submitted, accepted and/or published during this period. This document contains the list of contributions classified by authors and keywords.

The introductory section includes reflections on the interrelationships between the themes addressed by the publications and the emerging lines of research. In the conclusion, a comparison is drawn with the outcomes of the [previous report \(year 1\)](#), and the relationship with the parallel construction of the RE-DWELL vocabulary is explained. The Annex contains the abstracts of the publications, which are also available in the [project website](#).

1. Introduction

This is the second in a series of three compendiums of scientific publications produced by early-stage researchers (ESRs) in the course of their PhD research in the RE-DWELL network. In the second year of activity, 31 conference contributions were made, including presentations (5), posters (1), abstracts (15), papers (5) and journal articles (5) (see Table 1).

The work of the REDWELL network has also included a vocabulary base (see Table 2) and a series of case studies as well as the ESRs providing additional material through blogs and social media posts through their growing networks. The vocabulary base indicates the breadth and diversity of research topics, but also key overarching concerns, most especially “affordable housing” (5 outputs) and “transdisciplinarity” (6 outputs) and multiple aspects of sustainability (9 outputs). These shared themes strongly corroborate the aim of RE-DWELL to provide a platform for a holistic analysis of affordable and sustainable housing, viewed through a transdisciplinary perspective, which transcends disciplinary boundaries and involves experts and non-experts.

The work of the ESRs in the second year shows a geographical range across Europe. The research encompassed: Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and the UK. Comparative analysis was noted in the first-year report as an emerging area, one developed further in the second year of the project. Many of the outputs were comparative in nature, encompassing individual research as well as new collaborations between the ESRs. This includes a collaborative conference paper by four of the ESRs on informality in Southern European contexts. A deeper look at the north-south divide also informs a key aspect of Andreas Panagidis’ work on Cyprus, exploring the importance of a southern perspective in considering the social implications of infrastructure and co-creation at the neighbourhood scale.

This interest in participative practices and active citizen engagement has emerged as a key concern for several of the researchers. Androniki Pappa is looking at the notion of urban commons and citizen partnerships in Bologna, Barcelona and Lisbon, while Carolina Martín is examining participative design in relation to housing customisation through Open Building principles. Effrosyni Roussou approaches the topic from the perspective of architectural education, and how the design studio can be rethought through participatory action research and co-creation that bridge outside of academia into real world scenarios. This work includes a collaborative paper with Pappa comparing educational co-creation projects in Portugal and Cyprus.

Much of this work centres on the neighbourhood scale, but others are applying the idea of participative practice to social housing and sustainability as well. Zoe Tzika is focusing on different models of cooperative housing in Catalonia, including the phenomenon of grant-of-use housing that has emerged recently. And in a collaboration with Saskia Furman, they are analysing Sustainable Assessment Tools to reconsider the interrelation of environmental and social sustainability to help address housing inequality.

This methodological concern for questioning preconceived categories carries into the work of Christophe Verrier, who challenges the idea of fixed definitions by examining how personal experience and varying contexts influence our understandings of social housing as a category. Similarly, Mahmoud Alsaeed is exploring the overlaps and differing methodologies between housing and sustainability research. This interest is used to explore more specific cases,

including a comparison of sustainability standards and the problems of housing association provision in England.

Building on the environmental side of sustainability, Anette Davis is analysing life cycle assessments as applied to industrialised housing design for disassembly. Tijn Croon's research looks at many aspects of energy poverty, including policy frameworks in government and social housing providers in the Netherlands and neighbouring countries. Policy also forms an important background for Alex Fernández's work on the social impacts of Croatian policies for mortgage subsidies. Marko Horvat is also looking at the Croatian context in relation to government policy, homelessness, and social integration.

Moving from these more macro social concerns, others are looking in-depth at the relationship between social sustainability and social housing on the scale of housing design. Aya Elghandour is examining the designer's role in linking health and well-being with affordability in housing, while Leonardo Ricaurte is exploring the social outcomes of housing design features by applying a capabilities approach to post-occupancy evaluation. Anna Martin is researching how trauma-informed design principles can influence social housing, as well as how changing class structures, including the conflicts between marginalised groups and precarious middle earners, are impacting housing provision.

The transdisciplinary nature of this emerging body of work is clear, from efforts to bridge education and academia with real world practice and citizen engagement, to mixed methodologies that draw simultaneously on environmental, economic and social parameters of sustainability, to regional comparisons in relation to neighbourhood design, social housing provision, and government housing policies.

Table 1. ESRs publications

ESR	References	Contribution type
ESR 1 Anette Davis	Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). <i>Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 78-82). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
ESR 2 Saskia Furman	Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 73-77). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
ESR 3 Christophe Verrier	Verrier, C. (2023, March). <i>Making sense of a new national context in comparative housing: personal and systemic reflections of a researcher's journey in France</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 23-25). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
ESR 4 Aya Elghandour	Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing</i> . In 21st ISQOLS Annual Conference, Rotterdam, the Netherlands.	Conference poster
	Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective</i> . In: Schweiker, M. et al. (Eds.), Proceedings of Healthy Buildings 2023 Europe (pp. 482-484). Aachen, Germany.	Conference extended abstract
ESR 5 Mahmoud Alsaeed	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2024, March). <i>A comparative analysis of UK sustainable housing standards</i> . In 7th Residential Building Design & Construction Conference, Pennsylvania, USA.	Conference paper
	Alsaeed, M., & Hadjri, K. (2023, March). <i>A systematic approach to mapping social housing challenges</i> . In Housing Studies Association Annual Conference 2023, Sheffield, United Kingdom.	Conference abstract
	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2023, March). <i>Mode 2 Science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 9-14).	Conference abstract

	Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	
ESR 6 Marko Horvat	Haffner, M., Horvat, M., & van Bortel, G. (2023, June). <i>The Comeback of the Dutch Social Landlords? History and Future Perspectives</i> . In European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2023, Lodz, Poland.	Conference paper
	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia</i> . In Tomić-Koludrović, I. et al. (Eds.), Book of Abstracts, 9th National Sociological Congress of the Croatian Sociological Society (pp. 38-39), Split, Croatia. http://hsd.hr/wp-content/uploads/sites/598/2023/05/Knjiga-sazetaka-2023.pdf	Conference abstract
	Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., & Horvat, M. (2023). Evolution and evaluation of the state of social rights of the homeless in Croatia. <i>Criminology & Social Integration</i> , 31 (1), 55-77. https://doi.org/10.31299/ksi.31.1.3	Journal article
ESR 7 Anna Martin	Martin, A. (2023, December). <i>Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector</i> . In Transformative Change in the Contested Fields of Care and Housing in Europe, Linz, Austria.	Conference paper
	Martin, A. (2023, June). <i>Clashing Vulnerabilities for the right to adequate housing. Marginalized groups vs. middle-income groups in a precarious housing situation</i> . In Clashing Vulnerabilities, Uppsala, Sweden.	Conference paper
ESR 8 Andreas Panagidis	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts</i> . In KAEBUP 2023 Conference, Nicosia, Cyprus.	Conference presentation
	Panagidis, A., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>Co-creation from the South: The case of Cyprus</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 54-57). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
	Panagidis, A. (2022, August). <i>Configurations of Fragmented Infrastructure: The case of Nicosia situated at the Global North-South interface</i> . In RC21 Conference: Ordinary Cities in Exceptional Times, Athens, Greece.	Conference abstract

ESR 9 Effrosyni Roussou	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts</i> . In KAEBUP 2023 Conference, Nicosia, Cyprus.	
	Panayi, C., Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, August). <i>Fostering transdisciplinarity and co-creation in architecture: from research to teaching and vice versa</i> . In EAAE Annual conference 2023 School of Architecture(s), Turin, Italy.	Conference paper
	Roussou, E., & Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>From teaching the commons to commoning teaching: towards a reflexive architectural education</i> . In SMOOTH: Educational Commons and Active Social Inclusion Conference, Volos, Greece.	Conference abstract
	Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 37-40). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
ESR 10 Zoe Tzika	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts</i> . In KAEBUP 2023 Conference, Nicosia, Cyprus.	Conference presentation
	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023, June). <i>Understanding community participation in cooperative housing using the capabilities approach</i> . In European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2023, Lodz, Poland.	Conference presentation
	Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 73-77). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia</i> . Revista de Arquitectura.	Journal article
ESR 11 Tijn Croon	Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands</i> . Building Research & Information.	Journal article (Q1)

	Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., & Mulder, P. (2023). <i>Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design</i> . Energy Policy, 177, 113579.	Journal article (Q1)
	Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023, March). <i>Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 15-18). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract
	Croon, T. (2022, August-September). <i>The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe</i> . In NHRC & WG Energy Efficiency, ENHR 2022, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference presentation
ESR 12 Alex Fernández	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK</i> . In Tomić-Koludrović, I. et al. (Eds.), Book of Abstracts, 9th National Sociological Congress of the Croatian Sociological Society (pp. 35-36), Split, Croatia. http://hsd.hr/wp-content/uploads/sites/598/2023/05/Knjiga-sazetaka-2023.pdf	Conference abstract
	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). <i>The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK</i> . Critical Housing Analysis, 10(1), 50-65. https://dx.doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2023.10.1.553	Journal article (Q2)
ESR 13 Androniki Pappa	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts</i> . In KAEBUP 2023 Conference, Nicosia, Cyprus.	Conference presentation
	Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>Urban commons and the City: Framing the urban commons through institutional policies of public-civic collaboration</i> . In 8th Colóquio Arquitetura dos Territórios Metropolitanos Contemporâneos 2023, Lisbon, Portugal.	Conference presentation
	Roussou, E., & Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>From teaching the commons to commoning teaching: towards a reflexive architectural education</i> . In SMOOTH: Educational Commons and Active Social Inclusion Conference, Volos, Greece.	Conference abstract
	Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023, March). <i>Local partnerships and urban governance: The case of Lisbon</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 58-61).	Conference abstract

	Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	
ESR 14 Carolina Martín	Martín, C. (2023). <i>Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation</i> . In 8th Colóquio Arquitetura dos Territórios Metropolitanos Contemporâneos 2023, Lisbon, Portugal.	Conference presentation
ESR 15 Leonardo Ricaurte	Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). <i>New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 32-36). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327	Conference abstract

Table 2. Keywords and publications

Active citizenship	Panagidis, A., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>Co-creation from the South: The case of Cyprus.</i>
Adequate housing	Martin, A. (2023, June). <i>Clashing Vulnerabilities for the right to adequate housing. Marginalized groups vs. middle-income groups in a precarious housing situation.</i>
Affordable housing / housing affordability	Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). <i>Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach.</i> Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective.</i> Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing.</i> Haffner, M., Horvat, M., & van Bortel, G. (2023, June). <i>The Comeback of the Dutch Social Landlords? History and Future Perspectives.</i> Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i>
Agency	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023, June). <i>Understanding community participation in cooperative housing using the capabilities approach.</i>
Approach	Alsaeed, M., & Hadjri, K. (2023, March). <i>A systematic approach to mapping social housing challenges.</i>
Architectural geography	Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). <i>New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design.</i>
Built environment	Martin, A. (2023, December). <i>Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector.</i> Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023, June). <i>Understanding community participation in cooperative housing using the capabilities approach.</i>
Case study	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023, June). <i>Understanding community participation in cooperative housing using the capabilities approach.</i>
Civil organisations	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia.</i>
Clashing vulnerabilities	Martin, A. (2023, June). <i>Clashing Vulnerabilities for the right to adequate housing. Marginalized groups vs. middle-income groups in a precarious housing situation.</i>

Co-creation	Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023, March). <i>Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners.</i>
Collective housing	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i>
Commons	Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden.</i> Roussou, E., & Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>From teaching the commons to commoning teaching: towards a reflexive architectural education.</i>
Communal living	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i>
Community	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i>
Community-engaged design	Panayi, C., Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, August). <i>Fostering transdisciplinarity and co-creation in architecture: from research to teaching and vice versa.</i>
Comparative housing policies	Verrier, C. (2023, March). <i>Making sense of a new national context in comparative housing: personal and systemic reflections of a researcher's journey in France.</i>
Cradle-to-Cradle	Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). <i>Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach.</i>
Design	Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective.</i> Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing.</i>
Design and build pedagogy	Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden.</i>
Design for disassembly	Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). <i>Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach.</i>
East European housing	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). <i>The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>

Energy poverty	<p>Croon, T. (2022, August-September). <i>The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe</i>.</p> <p>Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands</i>.</p> <p>Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., & Mulder, P. (2023). <i>Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design</i>.</p> <p>Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023, March). <i>Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners</i>.</p>
Energy transition	<p>Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., & Mulder, P. (2023). <i>Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design</i>.</p> <p>Croon, T. (2022, August-September). <i>The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe</i>.</p>
England / UK housing	<p>Alsaeed, M., & Hadjri, K. (2023, March). <i>A systematic approach to mapping social housing challenges</i>.</p> <p>Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2024, March). <i>A comparative analysis of UK sustainable housing standards</i>.</p> <p>Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands</i>.</p> <p>Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective</i>.</p> <p>Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing</i>.</p>
Environmental sustainability	<p>Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators</i>.</p>
Evidence-based research	<p>Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts</i>.</p>
Financialization	<p>Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK</i>.</p>

Fit-out systems	Martín, C. (2023). <i>Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation.</i>
Flexible design	Martín, C. (2023). <i>Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation.</i>
Fuel poverty	Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., & Mulder, P. (2023). <i>Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design.</i> Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
France	Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Growth regime	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>
Health and wellbeing	Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective.</i> Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing.</i>
Home ownership	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). <i>The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>
Homeless	Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., & Horvat, M. (2023). <i>Evolution and evaluation of the state of social rights of the homeless in Croatia.</i> Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia.</i>
Household health	Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective.</i> Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing.</i>
Housing	Alsaeed, M., & Hadjri, K. (2023, March). <i>A systematic approach to mapping social housing challenges.</i> Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., & Horvat, M. (2023). <i>Evolution and evaluation of the state of social rights of the homeless in Croatia.</i>

Housing allocation	Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Housing associations	Haffner, M., Horvat, M., & van Bortel, G. (2023, June). <i>The Comeback of the Dutch Social Landlords? History and Future Perspectives.</i>
Housing customisation	Martín, C. (2023). <i>Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation.</i>
Housing crises	Martin, A. (2023, June). <i>Clashing Vulnerabilities for the right to adequate housing. Marginalized groups vs. middle-income groups in a precarious housing situation.</i>
Housing design	Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). <i>New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design.</i>
Housing economics	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). <i>The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>
Housing finance	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). <i>The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>
Housing policy	Croon, T. (2022, August-September). <i>The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe.</i> Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>
Housing research	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2023, March). <i>Mode 2 Science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability.</i>
Housing studies	Verrier, C. (2023, March). <i>Making sense of a new national context in comparative housing: personal and systemic reflections of a researcher's journey in France.</i>
Industrialised construction	Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). <i>Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach.</i>
Informal urbanism	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts.</i>

Knowledge production and transfer	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2023, March). <i>Mode 2 Science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability.</i>
Life Cycle Assessment	Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). <i>Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach.</i>
Live studio	Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden.</i> Panayi, C., Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, August). <i>Fostering transdisciplinarity and co-creation in architecture: from research to teaching and vice versa.</i>
Local partnerships	Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023, March). <i>Local partnerships and urban governance: The case of Lisbon.</i>
Mode 2 Science	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2023, March). <i>Mode 2 Science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability.</i>
Mortgage subsidy	Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i>
Netherlands	Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Open building	Martín, C. (2023). <i>Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation.</i>
Participation	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i>
Participatory budget	Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023, March). <i>Local partnerships and urban governance: The case of Lisbon.</i>
Pestoff	Haffner, M., Horvat, M., & van Bortel, G. (2023, June). <i>The Comeback of the Dutch Social Landlords? History and Future Perspectives.</i>
Planning	Panagidis, A. (2022, August). <i>Configurations of Fragmented Infrastructure: The case of Nicosia situated at the Global North-South interface.</i>
Policy	Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>Urban commons and the City: Framing the urban commons through institutional policies of public-civic collaboration.</i>

Policy prototyping	Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023, March). <i>Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners.</i>
Post-occupancy evaluation	Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). <i>New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design.</i>
Poverty gap	Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., & Mulder, P. (2023). <i>Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design.</i>
Public-civic collaboration	Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>Urban commons and the City: Framing the urban commons through institutional policies of public-civic collaboration.</i>
Quality of life	Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). <i>New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design.</i>
Renovation	Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Rent setting	Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Risk society	Martin, A. (2023, June). <i>Clashing Vulnerabilities for the right to adequate housing. Marginalized groups vs. middle-income groups in a precarious housing situation.</i>
Service providers	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia.</i>
Social exclusion	Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., & Horvat, M. (2023). <i>Evolution and evaluation of the state of social rights of the homeless in Croatia.</i>
Social housing	Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023, March). <i>Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners.</i> Croon, T. (submitted). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i> Haffner, M., Horvat, M., & van Bortel, G. (2023, June). <i>The Comeback of the Dutch Social Landlords? History and Future Perspectives.</i>
Social integration	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia.</i>
Social policies	Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., & Horvat, M. (2023). <i>Evolution and evaluation of the state of social rights of the homeless in Croatia.</i>

Social policy	Croon, T. (2022, August-September). <i>The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe.</i>
Social rental	Haffner, M., Horvat, M., & van Bortel, G. (2023, June). <i>The Comeback of the Dutch Social Landlords? History and Future Perspectives.</i>
Social rights	Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., & Horvat, M. (2023). <i>Evolution and evaluation of the state of social rights of the homeless in Croatia.</i>
Social service	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia.</i>
Social sustainability	Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators.</i>
Social value	Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). <i>New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design.</i>
Socio-spatial process	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023, June). <i>Understanding community participation in cooperative housing using the capabilities approach.</i>
Southern Europe	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts.</i>
Spatial agency	Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden.</i>
Spatial negotiation	Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). <i>Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts.</i>
Supportive housing	Martin, A. (2023, December). <i>Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector.</i>
Sustainability	Martín, C. (2023). <i>Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation.</i>
Sustainability practices	Panayi, C., Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, August). <i>Fostering transdisciplinarity and co-creation in architecture: from research to teaching and vice versa.</i>
Sustainability research	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2023, March). <i>Mode 2 Science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability.</i>

Sustainable housing	<p>Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2024, March). <i>A comparative analysis of UK sustainable housing standards.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators.</i></p>
Sustainable measurement frameworks	<p>Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators.</i></p>
Sustainability standards	<p>Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2024, March). <i>A comparative analysis of UK sustainable housing standards.</i></p>
Targeted policy	<p>Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., & Mulder, P. (2023). <i>Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design.</i></p> <p>Croon, T. (2022, August-September). <i>The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe.</i></p>
Total Quality Assessment	<p>Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). <i>Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators.</i></p>
Transdisciplinarity	<p>Alsaeed, M., & Hadjri, K. (2023, March). <i>A systematic approach to mapping social housing challenges.</i></p> <p>Elghandour, A. (2023, June). <i>Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective.</i></p> <p>Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). <i>Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing.</i></p> <p>Martin, A. (2023, December). <i>Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector.</i></p> <p>Panayi, C., Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, August). <i>Fostering transdisciplinarity and co-creation in architecture: from research to teaching and vice versa.</i></p> <p>Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden.</i></p>
Trauma-informed design	<p>Martin, A. (2023, December). <i>Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector.</i></p>
Urban commons	<p>Pappa, A. (2023, May). <i>Urban commons and the City: Framing the urban commons through institutional policies of public-civic collaboration.</i></p>

Urban governance	<p>Panagidis, A., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>Co-creation from the South: The case of Cyprus.</i></p> <p>Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023, March). <i>Local partnerships and urban governance: The case of Lisbon.</i></p>
Urban infrastructure	<p>Panagidis, A. (2022, August). <i>Configurations of Fragmented Infrastructure: The case of Nicosia situated at the Global North-South interface.</i></p>
Urban Living Labs	<p>Panagidis, A., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). <i>Co-creation from the South: The case of Cyprus.</i></p>
Urban regeneration	<p>Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023, March). <i>Local partnerships and urban governance: The case of Lisbon.</i></p>
Welfare policy	<p>Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). <i>The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i></p>
Welfare state	<p>Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). <i>Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK.</i></p>
Wellbeing psychologically informed	<p>Martin, A. (2023, December). <i>Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector.</i></p>

2. Dissemination

The abstracts included in the Annex of this report have been published on the project website section “Dissemination: Publications” (Figure 1). Each publication on the website contains the abstract and keywords, as well as associated concepts, case studies and blog posts. In addition, a relational graph shows the links between the publication and the related items (Figure 2).

The screenshot shows the 'Publications' section of the RE-DWELL website. The page is titled 'Publications' and has a subtitle 'Contributions to conferences and journals made by ESRs in the course of their research'. There are four publication cards visible, each with a title, author(s), date, and a 'Read more' link. A right-hand sidebar contains a list of tags and categories, including 'affordable housing', 'community engagement', 'active citizenship', 'affordability', 'ESRS', 'SUPERVISORS', 'HABITAT', 'active citizenship', 'affordability', 'affordable housing', 'BIM', 'circular economy', 'civil organisations', 'co-creation', 'community', 'community-engaged design', and 'comparative housing'. The footer includes the RE-DWELL logo, a European Commission logo, and a list of links for Search, Network, Work packages, Training, Programs, Projects, Legal Information, Privacy policy, Terms & conditions, Cookies policy, Contact us, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube. A small copyright notice at the bottom right reads '© Design and programming by ABC Engineering and Architecture s.l & Cole'.

Figure 1. View of Publications in RE-DWELL website

Figure 2. View of a publication on the RE-DWELL website

3. Conclusions

The number of publications produced in this second year (31) has kept at the level of the previous one (34). There has been an increase in number of publications co-authored by various ESRs, one in previous year, three in the second. The deepening of the ESRs' research is reflected in the number of published articles, with five in this second year, two of which are Q1, and one is Q2.

With regard to the keywords used in the publications, a comparison of Table 2 in the [first](#) and second-year reports reveals an evolution in the terms employed, indicating shifts in research focus or emphasis. Some concepts have remained and become more consolidated, including key concepts for RE-DWELL research as “affordability”, “sustainability” and “transdisciplinarity”, as well as others: “co-creation”, “design-for-disassembly”, “energy poverty”, “energy transition”, “industrialized construction”, “life-cycle assessment”, “quality of life”, and “post-occupancy evaluation”. There have a set of terms emerging in the second year clearly focusing on social (“social exclusion”, “social integration”, “social policies”) and psychological aspects (“trauma-informed design”, “well-being psychological informed”); in financing (“financialization”, “housing economics”, “housing finance”, “mortgage subsidy”) and policies (“rent setting”, “social rental”, “public-civic collaboration”), and in design and building (“open building”). Other terms dealing with research methodologies have been used, such as “evidence-based research” and “total quality assessment”, which reflects a greater awareness of researchers to methodological issues.

In parallel to the publications, ESRs have continued with the collaborative construction of the RE-DWELL vocabulary. Some of the keywords used in the publications have been developed in the entries published in the last year, among them: [“affordability”](#), [“building decarbonisation”](#), [“collaborative governance”](#), [“community-led housing”](#), [“energy poverty”](#), [“energy retrofit”](#), [“housing affordability”](#), [“housing allowance”](#), [“indoor thermal comfort”](#), [“industrialized construction”](#), [“measuring affordability”](#), [“open building”](#), [“path dependence”](#), [“performance gap in retrofit”](#), [“placemaking”](#), [“post-occupancy evaluation”](#), [“public-civic partnership”](#), [“social value”](#), [“trauma-informed design”](#), and [“window guidance”](#),

Annex 1 – Abstracts

Alsaeed, M., & Hadjri, K. (2023, March). *A systematic approach to mapping social housing challenges*. In Housing Studies Association Annual Conference 2023, Sheffield, United Kingdom.

Abstract: The provision of social housing is a complex process with fundamental environmental, social and economic challenges facing housing associations in England. Despite the growing attention given to identifying and resolving these challenges, some of the results so far are fragmented. In addition, housing associations' responses are often described as uncertain and lacking transdisciplinary integration.

This research argues that solving problems in social housing requires a rigorous and systematic approach that identifies, maps and classifies these problems from a transdisciplinary perspective. This is in order to establish the ramifications of the problems across all disciplines involved in the different phases of housing provision.

A literature-based examination was used to identify the development processes and associated problems by discipline. This served as the basis for semi-structured interviews with key actors from housing associations in England to identify the most current and pressing issues in housing provision from a transdisciplinary perspective.

The resulting evidence-based and theoretically informed results and mapping comprise a trilogy of methodological, practical and organisational issues. A binary structured approach was proposed to contribute to the theoretical debates on social housing and to identify the links between the issues and the disciplines involved. The practical component is intended to guide housing associations to assess the challenges and impacts at different stages of development from a transdisciplinary perspective. In addition, this approach could be further developed as a comprehensive framework to include praxis recommendations to address the issues faced by housing developers.

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Keywords: approach, England, housing, transdisciplinarity

Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2023, March). *Mode 2 Science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference* (pp. 9-14). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: The field of housing research is very diverse, theoretically reliant and intertwined with politics, economics, social and, more recently, environmental studies. Sustainability research, on the other hand, is often perceived as a complicated, practice-oriented field that examines the interactions between the economic, social and environmental pillars of society. The links between housing and sustainability research are often described as ambiguous and thorny topics, and many scholars refer to them as bifurcated areas of study. As a result, researchers have developed and adapted different approaches to the way knowledge on these two critical areas is perceived and generated. The 'Mode II' science is a relatively new concept that calls for the production of context-oriented, scientifically

reliable and robust social knowledge and is most notable for its tendency towards a transdisciplinary approach.

The concern of this paper is with the methodological issues in how housing and sustainability research and knowledge is presented and produced by those who engage with it. A literature focused exploratory investigation was used to identify the most common methodological issues of both fields. In the end, a reasoned claim was made that the 'Mode II' of knowledge production is one of the appropriate approaches to address the methodological challenges of dealing with sustainability and housing. Yet, the claim requires further in-depth investigation leading to a better understanding of the true extent of the problem and the possibility to design an innovative framework for sustainable housing knowledge production.

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Keywords: housing research, knowledge production and transfer, Mode 2 Science, sustainability research

Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, K., & Nawratek, K. (2024, March). *A comparative analysis of UK sustainable housing standards*. In 7th Residential Building Design & Construction Conference, Pennsylvania, USA.

Abstract: The UK government has adopted several building standards, of which Net-zero energy homes, Net-zero carbon homes, Home Quality Mark, Passivhaus and Building Regulations form the basis for sustainable housing practices in the UK. Yet, in 2019, 49 per cent of housing developers were not familiar with or did not adopt all parts of these standards, citing complexity and increasing costs as barriers. The UK's ambition to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 has therefore increased pressure on the construction industry to adopt more sustainable housing practices.

We argue that the complexity, fragmentation and misunderstanding of sustainability standards must be overcome in order to effectively design sustainable housing. For this, a comprehensive mapping of existing sustainability standards is required. This study therefore aims, firstly, to identify sustainable housing standards and discuss their challenges and the timeline for their development and, secondly, to conduct a comparative analysis that identifies similarities, differences and relationships between standards and discuss their effectiveness in delivering sustainable housing.

A literature review was used to identify the relevant standards in practice in the UK. This served as the basis for a comparative analysis to identify the similarities, differences and relationships between these standards. A desktop analysis was also conducted using three social housing case studies in England to identify the building standards applied and to assess their effectiveness in terms of the project's environmental impact and its sustainability outcomes.

A binary structured approach was proposed to contribute to the theoretical debates on the UK sustainability standards and their interrelationships and similarities. The practical component is intended to help housing planners navigate the complexity of the regulations and to support the decision-making process based on the cost-benefit principle. Finally, this approach could be further developed as a comprehensive framework to include practical recommendations, including the actual costs of embedding sustainability in housing construction.

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Keywords: sustainability standards, sustainable housing, UK housing

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Abstract: Homelessness is becoming an increasing social problem, and this is reflected in the growing number of people in this status and the consequences that such a social status entails as the most extreme form of poverty and social exclusion. In Croatia, the status of the homeless was 'recognized' and regulated only in 2011 by the Law on Social Welfare. The paper starts from the right to decent housing as a fundamental human right, analyses the evolution and current state of the social rights of the homeless, starting from the 90s to more recent legal documents and policies, and critically analyses and interprets the results of earlier research concerning social rights, status and position homeless. It is concluded that the social rights of the homeless are inadequately defined and care for the homeless is a residual part of social care.

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Keywords: homeless, housing, social exclusion, social policies, social rights

Croon, T. (2022, August-September). *The Governance of Energy Poverty Alleviation: Comparative Analyses of Targeted Policies and Strategies across Europe*. In NHRC & WG Energy Efficiency, ENHR 2022, Barcelona, Spain.

Abstract: Energy price volatility is likely to remain high due to geopolitical uncertainty and the transformative transition towards low-carbon generation. However, the consequences of price peaks are unevenly distributed across society as households with low incomes, little savings, and inefficient dwellings are disproportionately affected. Energy poverty – the inability to secure sufficient domestic energy services that allow for participation in society – can have deteriorating effects on their livelihoods. Therefore, energy poverty alleviation has become an important policy and research area, not least in the context of the ‘Renovation Wave’, the European transition towards low-carbon housing. This dissertation explores opportunities for European policymakers and housing professionals to target vulnerable households at risk of energy poverty so that the Renovation Wave can be made into a ‘just transition’. It aims to contribute to an understanding of ‘recognitional justice’ in several ways. First, it

explores the added value of the energy poverty gap in assessing the intensity and inequality of deprivation caused by energy poverty. Moreover, these dimensions are used to identify driving household, dwelling and spatial characteristics of energy poverty in the Netherlands. Subsequently, it suggests targeted interventions that housing associations could implement to support those in need. It compares the regulatory opportunities and obstacles these housing providers face and assesses the target efficiency of state-level support policies in France, the UK, and the Netherlands. Finally, it develops a multilevel governance framework indicating and discussing the roles and responsibilities of actors in European energy poverty alleviation. The project uses a mix of quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive overview of how recognition justice can be integrated into policies across governance levels. By doing this, it aims to enhance identification of energy poverty, efficiency of alleviation policies and public accountability of actors responsible.

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Keywords: energy poverty, energy transition, housing policy, social policy, targeted policy

Croon, T. (submitted). *Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: Investigating targeted approaches in France, England, and the Netherlands*. Building Research & Information.

Abstract: Since energy prices across Europe started to rise in 2021, there has been growing concern of social housing tenants at risk of energy poverty. So far, studies have largely focused on the role of governments and on what tenants themselves could do. However, research has rarely considered specific targeting approaches by social housing providers (SHPs). This study explores the role of these stakeholders and investigates what policies French, English, and Dutch social housing providers could adopt to enhance the effectiveness of their energy poverty alleviation efforts. Focus groups with

practitioners demonstrated their perspectives on the most effective interventions, their respective benefits and challenges, and variation across policy contexts. We found that social housing professionals perceive a significant responsibility in addressing energy poverty among their tenants, but that there remains uncertainty regarding the distribution of responsibilities between stakeholders. While views and practices among professionals vary, most deem prioritisation of retrofits or behavioural interventions for those households in or at risk of energy poverty more effective and feasible approaches than setting rents or allocating dwellings in a targeted manner. Particularly the presence of institutional barriers and a lack of data hinder SHPs from implementing a more targeted approach in addressing energy poverty.

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Keywords: energy poverty, England, France, fuel poverty, housing allocation, Netherlands, renovation, rent setting, social housing

Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023, March). *Energy poverty alleviation in social housing: Prototyping policies with practitioners*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 15-18). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: The negative consequences of energy poverty have been known for decades, but the sense of urgency and subsequent establishment of policies have substantially differed across countries. One of the reasons mentioned in the literature is that insights from research are not adequately communicated to policymakers and practitioners. In parallel, the body of scholarship on energy poverty measurement has grown rapidly, but its use in practice has hardly been addressed. This project intends

to combat this mismatch, by proactively engaging with various housing association professionals across Europe to find out how qualitative and quantitative knowledge on energy poverty can inform retrofit strategies in different policy contexts. It examines the key role of housing associations with a significant share of their predominantly low-income tenants living in energy poverty in the ‘just transition’. Furthermore, it explores how their apparent techno-economic approach to retrofit provision could be altered by organizing focus groups with housing association professionals in France, the UK, and the Netherlands. Professionals from different departments will be urged to discuss whether, and if so why, they consider energy poverty to be a policy priority not only from a behavioural perspective but also from a housing quality perspective. We proactively work with them to learn how qualitative and quantitative knowledge on energy poverty can inform alleviation strategies in different policy contexts. The focus groups will be set up as ‘innovation journeys’, with the participants acting as ‘co-researchers’ or ‘co-designers’. First, I will give a brief explanation about energy poverty measurement. Then, assuming that the housing association is properly informed as to which households are most vulnerable, we will collectively explore the potentially alleviating policy interventions available. We will look at opportunities and obstacles regarding finance, staff capacity, and regulations, thus allowing for a comparison between the three countries. While the sessions will have a rather flexible structure, we will ensure that targeted retrofit is at the heart of the discussion (besides e.g., information provision, behavioural change, and rent policy). The study thus uses an abductive approach, ‘prototyping’ possible ways towards a desired policy outcome (energy poverty alleviation). It is an exploratory phase in which new policy interventions can be discovered and provisional guesses can be made concerning their effects.

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Keywords: co-creation, energy poverty, policy prototyping, social housing

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Abstract: Recent energy price spikes have led to increased energy poverty among low-income households living in inefficient homes. Accurate statistics on energy poverty help inform resource allocation and better target relief schemes and retrofit funds. Existing indicators are predominantly defined in terms of a headcount ratio – the share of population living below a certain threshold or poverty line. In this paper we draw from the literature on income poverty evaluation to argue that the use of more elaborate energy poverty gap indices can substantiate the design and monitoring of energy poverty policies, by not only considering incidence but also intensity and inequality of energy poverty across households. We demonstrate that the choice for a particular energy poverty (gap) indicator makes the implicit welfare choices of energy poverty policies explicit. We illustrate our arguments for the case of the Netherlands, using recently developed microdata statistics on energy poverty, and an imposed energy price shock. We show that spatial targeting of relief funds based on incidence would neglect the full depth of energy poverty deprivation. Finally, we argue that visualisation techniques from the income poverty literature help to comprehend different poverty orderings and draw comparisons between time periods, regions, and subgroups.

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Davis, A., & Quintana, A. (2023, March). *Rethinking housing as a kit-of-parts and shearing layers: An LCA approach*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 78-82)*. Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: There is growing interest to utilise Industrialised Construction (IC) in combination with Design for Disassembly (DfD) to provide sustainable and affordable housing based on circular economy principles. A circular approach to construction is a high priority in the EU and on a global scale, as highlighted by the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Europe-wide framework Level(s), and changes in leading Green Building assessments. These assessments are increasingly reliant on quantitative data and cradle-to-cradle Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) to measure resource and energy efficiency. However, applying a Whole Building LCA to industrialised housing designed for disassembly is an unresolved issue. Industry professionals apply different lifespans to conduct the assessment, which often do not take into account the varying lifespans of different building components.

It is important to use a reliable Whole Building LCA methodology that is aligned with sustainable construction practices, not only to appropriately measure and reduce the environmental impact of housing, but crucially to be able to define environmental targets at a policy level. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to improve the conventional Whole Building LCA methodology, for application to housing built using DfD in combination with IC. The long-term aim of the on-going research is to enable technical stakeholders to make better informed design decisions throughout all building stages and provide sustainable solutions based on more accurate information, within a less time-consuming process.

Within this paper, an adaptation of the ISO standards for LCA is proposed for large, prefabricated building components. This will be achieved by aggregating LCAs to form a cradle-to-cradle Whole Building LCA, which takes into consideration the different lifespans for building layers based on the Shearing Layers concept. To provide a more holistic overview of sustainability impacts, costing related to construction and maintenance and demolition will support the results. The methodology will be tested on research projects undertaken at the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV).

The expected outcome of this project is an outline methodology to be used in industry, which will include a roadmap and recommendations to achieve this.

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Keywords: affordable housing, cradle-to-cradle, design-for-disassembly, industrialised construction, life cycle assessment

Elghandour, A., & Hadjri, K. (2023, August). *Rethinking housing affordability to advocate the design for health and wellbeing*. In 21st ISQOLS Annual Conference, Rotterdam, the Netherlands.

Abstract: Poor housing conditions such as overcrowding, dampness, and inadequate thermal insulation often fall within the challenging realm of housing affordability. These conditions seriously risk a household's health and wellbeing (H+W) and the entire national health system. Decisions made during the design development stages of a residential building can contribute to both households' H+W and

housing affordability. This study presents a review to explore the connection between housing affordability, households' H+W, and design. It aims to highlight the designers' role in advocating the rights of households' H+W in the design process of affordable housing. The review is carried out to achieve the following objectives: (1) to understand the common measuring methods of housing affordability to identify its potential to inform design stages, (2) to draw designers' attention to some of the current global challenges on H+W and affordability such as housing prices, energy poverty, and Covid-19 pandemic, (4) Identify the areas where design can contribute to H+W and housing affordability. The review revealed four key factors to be incorporated when labelling a house as "Affordable" to respect households' H+W. It also identified four housing affordability goals for designers and providers to support low-income households' H+W resilience during stressful times. In addition, three cost-related categories have been identified where design can contribute to housing affordability.

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Prochorskaite, A., et al (2016). Housing Stakeholder Preferences for the "Soft" Features of Sustainable and Healthy Housing Design in the UK. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.

Keywords: design, England, health and wellbeing, household health, housing affordability, transdisciplinarity, UK housing

Elghandour, A. (2023, June). *Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective*. In: Schweiker, M. et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of Healthy Buildings 2023 Europe* (pp. 482-484). Aachen, Germany.

Abstract: Household health and wellbeing (H+W) is one of the most important determinants of public health. In the UK, the impact of poor housing costs the National Health Service (NHS) over £1 billion a year. In times of economic challenge, these pressures can increase. On the one hand, low- and low-to-middle-income communities may sacrifice their standard of living to reduce spending. On the other hand, with the housing crisis, there is a risk that unfit properties will be deemed affordable, overlooking aspects of H+W.

Design can play a key role through the decisions made at the design development stages, therefore helping to reduce these pressures on the public sector and remove potential risks. For example,

decisions on parameters of the size, position and material of windows affect daylight and noise levels, connectedness with nature, and the residents' sense of privacy, the lack of which have been linked to mental health symptoms in Europe, according to the World Health Organization (WHO). These parameters also influence ventilation and thermal comfort and therefore correlate with mould growth and respiratory illnesses. So far, the literature on the impact of design on household H+W is fragmented when it comes to guiding the design process of affordable homes.

Moreover, there is a lack of a comprehensive perspective on the design of healthy homes that promote wellbeing and yet are affordable. Therefore, this study will take a transdisciplinary approach to promote mutual learning between housing stakeholders engaged in the design and affordability of housing, and the health and wellbeing of households, in order to inform the study. This approach aims to explore and map existing knowledge to demonstrate the potential contribution of designers to the H+W of household members. To this end, an extensive literature review and interviews with stakeholders from the health and housing sectors will be conducted. This would enable the development of a design taxonomy for household H+W, to provide an effective tool for designers to prioritize the household H+W and support their decision-making during the design process.

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Keywords: affordable housing, design, England, health and wellbeing, household health, transdisciplinarity, UK housing

Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). Uloga hipotekarnih subvencija u strategiji hrvatskog gospodarskog rasta: političko-ekonomski pristup SSK-u. The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK. In Tomić-Koludrović, I. et al. (Eds.), Book of Abstracts, 9th National Sociological Congress of the Croatian

Sociological Society (pp. 35-36), Split, Croatia. <http://hsd.hr/wp-content/uploads/sites/598/2023/05/Knjiga-sazetaka-2023.pdf>

Abstract: Since 2017, Croatian housing policy has focused on promoting homeownership through the SSK programme – a form of mortgage subsidisation that covers a proportion of housing costs. Although this policy aimed to improve affordability and increase homeownership, a recent economic evaluation has shown that the SSK has in fact contributed to rising house prices and has been ineffective at raising the homeownership rate. While econometric research has identified the impact that the SSK has had on house price volatility and affordability, the underlying factors leading to the implementation of this subsidy, as well as its broader societal impacts, remain under-researched. Through a political-economy lens, this paper analyses the context that led to the inception of the SSK, its core targeting principles, and its impact on the housing market. We ask: How does this subsidy position the Croatian housing market within the national strategy for economic growth and social policy provision? We argue that this policy's impact on housing markets is twofold. First, the SSK reinforces a shift towards financialised growth through increased asset prices. Second, this subsidy shifts the focus of social policy towards mortgage markets, thereby furthering the privatisation of the welfare state and favouring middle income groups. This paper's contribution resides in critically discussing the SSK beyond its stated goals and contextualising it within the broader model of economic growth dependent on private finance. Through interviews with relevant stakeholders, descriptive data indicators, and a review of policy documents, this paper characterises the Croatian growth strategy as a form of small-scale financialization that relies on aligning social policy with mortgage markets. Finally, we position the SSK within a wider array of finance-led housing policies and suggest the formulation of a comprehensive housing strategy tailored to the broader segments of Croatian society. This research is part of Horizon 2020, a Marie Curie ITN project, RE-DWELL Delivering Affordable and Sustainable Housing in Europe.

Keywords: financialization, growth regime, housing policy, mortgage subsidy, welfare state

Fernández, A., & Bežovan, G. (2023). *The Role of Mortgage Subsidies in the Croatian Economic Growth Strategy: a Political-Economy Approach to the SSK*. *Critical Housing Analysis*, 10(1), 50-65. <https://dx.doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2023.10.1.553>

Abstract: Since 2017, Croatian housing policy has focused on promoting homeownership through the SSK programme – a form of mortgage subsidisation that covers a proportion of housing costs. Although this policy aimed to improve affordability and increase homeownership, a recent economic evaluation has shown that the SSK has in fact contributed to rising house prices and has been ineffective at raising the homeownership rate. While econometric research has identified the impact that the SSK has had on house price volatility and affordability, the underlying factors leading to the implementation of this subsidy, as well as its broader societal impacts, remain under-researched. Through a political-economy lens, this paper analyses the context that led to the inception of the SSK, its core targeting principles, and its impact on the housing market. We ask: How does this subsidy position the Croatian housing market within the national strategy for economic growth and social policy provision? We argue that this policy's impact on housing markets is twofold. First, the SSK reinforces a shift towards financialised growth through increased asset prices. Second, this subsidy shifts the focus of social policy towards mortgage markets, thereby furthering the privatisation of the welfare state and favouring middle income groups. This paper's contribution resides in critically discussing the SSK beyond its stated goals and contextualising it within the broader model of economic growth dependent on private finance. Through interviews with relevant stakeholders, descriptive data indicators, and a review of policy documents, this paper characterises the Croatian growth strategy as a form of small-scale financialization that relies on aligning social policy with mortgage markets. Finally, we position the SSK within a wider array of finance-led housing policies and

suggest the formulation of a comprehensive housing strategy tailored to the broader segments of Croatian society.

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Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2023, May). *Analiza održivosti sustava socijalne integracije beskućnika u Hrvatskoj / Analysis of the sustainability of the homeless social integration system in Croatia.* In Tomić-Koludrović, I. et al. (Eds.), *Book of Abstracts, 9th National Sociological Congress of the Croatian Sociological Society* (pp. 38-39), Split, Croatia. <http://hsd.hr/wp-content/uploads/sites/598/2023/05/Knjiga-sazetaka-2023.pdf>

Abstract: Homelessness is a complex social problem facing large cities in Croatia, a country that has made the transition from state socialism to a free market economy. During this period, the “give-away” privatisation of public rental housing took place and the state withdrew from the housing market, which is increasingly dominated by speculative interests. In view of the increasing number of homeless

people, the government introduced programmes in 2011 to care for the homeless, which are managed by the major cities. The existing social integration programmes for the homeless are mainly run by civil society organisations. Previous studies have analysed the causes of homelessness and their demographic characteristics. The achievements of innovative practices such as “Housing First” speak to certain positive outcomes. This paper reflects the current status of homelessness in Croatia by looking at national and local policies, and briefly introduces how homelessness is perceived in the neighbouring transitional (ex-communist) countries. The paper aims to understand the sustainability of the system of social integration of homeless people in Croatia, taking into account three components: financial sustainability of organisations, institutional capacity and social sustainability. The data collection was conducted through a survey, and a focus group is planned to follow. The research will provide answers to the main challenges related to the sustainability of organisations dealing with the social inclusion of homeless people and propose the necessary measures that would strengthen the system and thus contribute to more efficient and effective policies in the system. The research findings will be presented to the public and placed in the context of necessary policy changes.

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Keywords: civil organisations, homeless, service providers, social integration, social service

Martin, A. (2023, December). *Housing and Healing: The role of trauma informed design in the supportive housing sector*. In *Transformative Change in the Contested Fields of Care and Housing in Europe*, Linz, Austria.

Abstract: The built environment profoundly impacts our mental, emotional, and physical well-being and promotes empowerment. This study explores the role of trauma-informed design in the supportive housing sector, where people often live with complex needs. This conceptual paper aims to bring together the knowledge and expertise of academic and non-academic members of our society, particularly those in the housing and care sector, to explore the opportunities and challenges of implementing psychologically informed design principles.

The paper's first section consists of a comprehensive review of existing literature, examining how contemporary positive psychology and trauma theory principles can be applied to physical settings. The focus is on utilizing adjustable and flexible design codes that prioritize positive outcomes and social impact. Moving forward, the second part of the paper builds upon the findings of forty in-depth semi-structured interviews. These interviews were carefully recorded and analysed with NVivo, following the logic of grounded theory. The diverse responses revealed both trends and differing perspectives on the role of trauma-informed design. Therefore, real-life examples mentioned by interviewees were chosen to illustrate potential ways to address contested care and housing needs with the help of various funding mechanisms.

Ultimately, the paper argues that considering the fundamental principles of trauma-informed design should be a crucial aspect of any effective social housing program, whether at the European, national, or local level. The results of this study go beyond the boundaries of specific scientific disciplines, offering a convergence of different theoretical perspectives. By considering sustainability as a matter of communicative rationality, this paper seeks to promote a holistic approach to designing supportive housing environments that prioritize the well-being of individuals with complex needs.

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Keywords: built environment, supportive housing, transdisciplinarity, trauma-informed design, well-being psychologically informed

Martin, A. (2023, June). *Clashing Vulnerabilities for the right to adequate housing. Marginalized groups vs. middle-income groups in a precarious housing situation.* In *Clashing Vulnerabilities*, Uppsala, Sweden.

Abstract: The globalization era resulted in the fragmentation of class structures, and inequalities grew. As a result, upward mobility is declining in most countries in Europe. More and more people from the middle classes are at risk of downward mobility, but they are classified as “not poor enough” to receive help and are pushed back of the queue for benefits, including housing. They face safety concerns, as they can only access unhealthy, low-quality, energy-inefficient, or overcrowded housing options. Their situation has become fragile partly because of the liberalized labour market, or the system abandoned them due to the cuts in the welfare state. Meanwhile, the number of evicted and homeless people is also rising. As a result, there are “clashing vulnerabilities” between marginalized people (including the zone of “disaffiliation”) and increasingly downwardly mobile people from the low and middle cases. Deepening the housing crises these vulnerable groups are competing in terms of resources and administrative capacities.

The paper examines these clashing vulnerabilities between marginalized people and increasingly downwardly mobile people from the low and middle classes. Risks are distributed differently, and the

probability of becoming downwardly mobile has structural and individual factors. These factors are analysed with mixed methods, exploring the new meaning(s) of risk society.

The paper argues that the market needs to be very carefully regulated. Recognizing the significance of housing as a fundamental need, it is crucial to allocate a significant proportion of tax revenues towards its stability and to implement improved regulations, to create an environment that promotes fairness, transparency, and accountability. On the one hand, social and housing policies should lower the number of people who are homeless (living literally on the streets), and on the other hand, they should provide people in general with more opportunities to get safe, affordable homes. Funds should be utilized to establish programs that provide financial assistance, promote affordable housing initiatives, and support sustainable development practices.

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Keywords: adequate housing, clashing vulnerabilities, housing crises, risk society

Martín, C. (2023). *Open Building as a design approach for housing customisation*. In 8th Colóquio Arquitetura dos Territórios Metropolitanos Contemporâneos 2023, Lisbon, Portugal.

Abstract: The increased demand for housing due to demographic growths and urban agglomerations is one of the critical issues concerning today's cities. The vast majority of the residential building stock has become obsolete, as a result of post-war rigid typologies. In most of the cases, the current housing production does not consider the integration of the user in the decision-making process, nor it offers flexible solutions that can accommodate different needs.

This paper aims to connect the Open Building principles and methodology to the current challenges that the housing industry is facing. The study will examine the contribution of the concept to the housing industry from a social, organisational, and technical perspective.

The results will aim to shed some light over the potential of the Open Building's design approach to increase the resiliency of residential buildings, include new actors in the decision-making process, and ensure the in-built capacity of these buildings to renew themselves and adapt over time.

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Keywords: fit-out systems, flexible design, housing customisation, open building, sustainability

Panagidis, A. (2022, August). *Configurations of Fragmented Infrastructure: The case of Nicosia situated at the Global North-South interface*. In RC21 Conference: Ordinary Cities in Exceptional Times, Athens, Greece.

Abstract: The processes of modernisation and urbanisation in Cyprus by previous colonial administrations aimed to replicate the “modern infrastructure ideal” (Graham & Marvin, 2001) and exert social control (Sioulas & Pyla, 2018). The newly established planning department undertook large infrastructural engineering projects related to water supply, electrification and road networks which largely determined the form of urbanisation. Subsequent Greek-Cypriot administrations adopting earlier planning mechanisms, have mainly followed technocratic formulae and the dominance of politics over civil society (Mavratsas, 1998; Trimikliniotis, 2001). Moreover, the processes of the island’s urbanisation are situated at the “interface” between the planning rationalities of the global North and the lived realities of the global South (Watson, 2009). Nicosia, the capital city, is characterised by dispersed, low-density urban development, incessant parcellation of land and the overwhelming dominance of private car mobility (Constantinides, 2018; Ioannou, 2016) resulting in great deficiencies and fragmentations of urban infrastructures. Such political and spatial incongruities are conveyed by pockets of entitlement contrasted by the informal practices and claims to urban space through which under-resourced citizens perpetually strive to adapt and improvise. However, the social implications of disjointed and dispersed infrastructures have been greatly overlooked. In addition, despite being a country that has remained a “post colony” striving to be modern as characterised by Argyrou (2010), Cyprus is rarely examined from the perspectives of postcolonial urban theory or urban informality when speaking about urban planning or housing.

This paper focuses on the relation between the physical and social attributes of Nicosia’s peripheral expansion apparent in people’s daily confrontations with fragmented infrastructures. Using suburban infrastructure as a frame of examination, the method of visual ethnography is used in order to trace the socio-material practices that point to heterogeneous arrangements. These include among others, side-of-the-road vendors, do-it-yourself advertisements, improvised agricultural practices and informal home extensions. Furthermore, physical evidence of the lived, grounded realities that resist dominant land use configurations is juxtaposed with spatial planning logics. The paper highlights the need for a critical, Southern perspective of investigation, revealing human-infrastructure interactions that contest normative planning positions and North-South binaries. Therefore, this study aims to determine whether an “ordinary” geography of human-infrastructure interactions may lead to envisioning development processes that re-politicise land and infrastructure to shed light on alternative planning pathways that refute inherited trajectories of modernisation.

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Keywords: planning, urban infrastructure

Panagidis, A., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). *Co-creation from the South: The case of Cyprus*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference* (pp. 54-57). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: Dominated by a technocratic state and a form of “Greek-Cypriot corporatism” (Mavratsas, 1998), civil society in Cyprus has been found to be underdeveloped (CIVICUS, 2011). This is reflected in the lack of citizen participation and the lack of decision-making power of the many people dwelling and working in the margins between the powerful state and the market to negotiate decisions. Informal and co-produced urban spaces (here understood as spontaneously co-produced) by actors who “do not typically fit into state-led and ‘professional’ planning schemes” (Galuszka, 2019, p. 144) are common,

yet not recognised or institutionalised. These characteristics place Cyprus in the discussions around citizenship and participation in the global South.

In the meantime, new urban governance arrangements are on the agenda of many European governments promoting “active citizenship” and social innovation concerning the decision-making processes that involve citizens in the planning and provision of housing and public services (Bisschops & Beunen, 2019; Boonstra, 2015; Garcia & Haddock, 2016; Morgan, 2018). Furthermore, recent research is increasingly emphasising co-creation (Davis & Andrew, 2017; Koster, 2015) - the sharing of decision-making powers between municipalities, citizens and other actors – and this term is being applied in housing development and urban regeneration experiments at the neighbourhood scale. Innovative governance processes encouraging self-organisation to engage citizens beyond participation in planning are being investigated in settings labelled by the terms Urban Living Labs (ULLs), city labs or citizen innovation labs. In ULLs the joint knowledge and abilities of citizens, urban professionals, and local authorities is mobilised in collaborative environments where innovation can take place in real-life settings.

However, as these novel approaches are being transferred mainly from Northern cities to Southern Europe, there is a need to investigate co-creation by “seeing from the South” (Watson, 2009) as well as to avoid the mistake of applying a universal concept to contexts which to date have been perceived at the fringes of urbanity. In support of the “peripheral turn” in urban studies, it is important to challenge general guidelines that are replicated, including ULLs, and to adapt these novel governance approaches to their respective contexts (Galuszka, 2019). The ways in which civic engagement is fostered in Cyprus, especially regarding matters of urban development and informality, will form the main research question.

This paper aims to add to the theoretical discussion of co-creation, social innovation and active citizenship from a “southern” perspective, including the overlapping interpretations of the global South and Southern Europe. It will challenge existing parameters and guidelines of civic engagement and innovation in urban planning and housing by exploring the need to develop a southern perspective of co-creation. The goal is to enhance the diversity of southern perspectives of urban theory, to challenge assumptions around best practices of sustainable urban development, but also to improve the methodology of applying co-creation to tackle housing and planning issues in postcolonial contexts.

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Keywords: active citizenship, urban governance, urban living labs

Panayi, C., Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, August). *Fostering transdisciplinarity and co-creation in architecture: from research to teaching and vice versa*. EAAE Annual conference 2023 School of Architecture(s), Turin, Italy.

Abstract: The Co-creation design studio, at the Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus, has been acting as a meeting place for students, educators, researchers, citizens, and external stakeholders since 2021, aiming to bridge gaps between architectural research, pedagogy, civil society, and local governance bodies through a transdisciplinary pedagogical framework. Acknowledging that many societal challenges are complex and multifaceted and cannot be adequately addressed by any single discipline or sector alone, the Co-creation studio focuses on the co-production of knowledge with stakeholders outside of academia. This entails involving them from the outset of the project, as well as co-designing design activities and proposals that are relevant to their needs and interests, ensuring a grounded process in real-world challenges.

The studio’s pedagogical framework and methodology have been designed, implemented, and evaluated three times until now, through participatory action research methodology, investigating the impact on the design result, on the development of skills for the students, and their attitude towards their role as future professionals. The paper highlights the findings of these three years of research, with a reflective way, suggesting future steps for improvement. Its long-term repetition will gradually

build a knowledge base, aiming to revisit existing educational methods, to respond to current and future challenges in an efficient and inclusive way.

Keywords: community-engaged design, live studio, sustainability practices, transdisciplinarity

Pappa, A. (2023, May). *Urban commons and the City: Framing the urban commons through institutional policies of public-civic collaboration*. In 8th Colóquio Arquitetura dos Territórios Metropolitanos Contemporâneos 2023, Lisbon, Portugal.

Abstract: Urban commons is an emerging paradigm in Europe that has gained growing attention in recent years reflected both in the rising literature around its multiple facets and in a blossoming of collective practices of co-creation and stewardship in the urban space. Advocating sharing and collaborative management of urban resources, such as housing, energy and public space, urban commons initiatives foster the reclaiming of fundamental rights in the city⁹ and are hence seen as a response to challenges posed by the neoliberal management of resources, privatisation, and urbanisation trends, such as gentrification. Traditionally these initiatives are principally self-organised, yet there is an increasing support by municipalities worldwide in forming policies and institutions that promote the collaborative regeneration of urban spaces into urban commons as an attempt to democratise the urban governance and involve citizens in the decision-making processes that affect their neighbourhoods and lives. However, the relationship between state or the City and urban commons is being addressed in an ongoing debate in scholarly discourses, examining whether and in what conditions the emancipatory social processes of commoning should be institutionalised and conformed into regulations. This paper examines the definition of the urban commons spaces in literature and its interpretation by municipal policies that are explicitly implementing regulatory frameworks around their development and sustainability. Based on a theoretical review on the urban commons, the defining parameters upon which the policies are analysed are the resources, people or institutions that manage them and social processes of governing them. The paper analyses two paradigmatic institutional cases of regenerating urban commons developed in Bologna and Barcelona under different contexts, juxtaposing their two approaches in sharing the management and responsibility of the public assets with citizens and local organisations. It concludes by underscoring the contributions of the two policies, inclining or different, in the conceptualisation of the urban commons. An anticipated extension of this first step would be the project-scale examination of the policies to understand if and how the ownership transfer of the public assets contributes to true urban commons Practices.

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Keywords: policy, public-civic collaboration, urban commons

Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023, March). *Local partnerships and urban governance: The case of Lisbon*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference* (pp. 58-61). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: Collaborative forms of governance in urban regeneration are increasingly gaining ground in cities around the world, contributing to the active engagement of citizens in decision-making processes that affect their neighbourhoods and lives. In some cases, municipalities even attempt to embrace local grassroots initiatives led by active citizens, who creatively invent ways to regain and co-manage the urban commons. Extrapolated In the urban scale, such initiatives create networks of social practices of commoning that foster platforms of individual and collective rights (Stavrides, 2016) and help citizens reclaim the urban value (Borch & Kornberger, 2015).

In a similar vision, the Department of Housing and Local Development of the Municipality of Lisbon launched in 2011 a participatory budget program, namely BIP/ZIP, that serves as an instrument of public policy. The aim of BIP/ZIP is to annually fund bottom-up initiatives led by local partnerships in 67 priority neighbourhoods that enable responses to social and territorial emergencies. As of its 2021 edition, the program has funded 426 projects, involving 1403 different partner entities.

The aim of this research is to investigate the matrix of local partnerships that have been formulated throughout the eleven years of BIP/ZIP and understand their dynamic role for the city of Lisbon. The methodology employs data analysis and qualitative coding methods (Saldana, 2021) to (i) a map the complex networks of partners, and (ii) explore the transformation of the urban governance through the emerging roles of different types of partners – organisations.

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Keywords: local partnerships, participatory budget, urban governance, urban regeneration

Pappa, A., Tzika, Z., Roussou, E., & Panagidis, A. (2023, December). *Informality as evidence: ethnographic insights from Southern European contexts*. In KAEBUP 2023 Conference, Nicosia, Cyprus.

Abstract: The rising interest in evidence-based practices for urban planning has opened up a pool of tools and methods that transform design processes and foster informed decision-making. While digital tools, big data and simulations provide codified evidence imperative for urban research, they significantly focus on the ‘big picture’ which often neglects the gaps between formal planning and everyday life at a local level. By reflecting upon heterogeneous socio-spatial arrangements produced through daily appropriation tactics, informality is framed as evidence for planning and design. The focus of the paper is on underrepresented groups that reclaim their participation through the configuration of everyday spaces. at four countries of the European South: Spain, Greece, Cyprus and Portugal. Following an ethnographic approach, and using photography as a grounded research method, practices of informal and direct participation, which are often overlooked, are being acknowledged, analysed and compared. Identifying instances of urban informality as alternatives to formal processes of urban development, reveals traces of negotiation, claims to space, exclusion, but also collaboration and sharing. The selected cases are juxtaposed, looking at their constitutive characteristics, motives, target groups, agencies, tactics, relation with the state and finally their contribution in the urban informality discourse. As a result, the paper seeks to recognise, firstly, informality as a legitimate source of knowledge in the urban planning debates, and secondly, the importance of incorporating ethnographic approaches in evidence-based design and planning.

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Keywords: evidence-based research, informal urbanism, Southern Europe, spatial negotiation

Ricaurte, L. (2023, March). *New approaches to post-occupancy Evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference* (pp. 32-36). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: This research focuses on identifying the spaces that are crucial in yielding the well-being and quality of life of residents in housing schemes. Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE) is a promising method for assessing a building’s adequacy to meet social impact goals, comply with building regulations, and deliver improved sustainability and affordability, but it tends to focus on environmental outcomes rather than the less tangible social outcomes (Hay et al., 2017; RIBA &

MacDonald P., 2020; Samuel, 2020). When it comes to housing, a decision about the height of a bench in a common space, the position of windows and porches in relation to a playground, or the size of a stairwell can affect the social value of a space, and only dialogue with inhabitants can bring these nuances to light. Although architects such as Herman Hertzberger (1963, 1991) have speculated about these effects, they have not yet been subject to systematic study or reconciled with contemporary debates about the social value of housing. In the field of urban design, for instance, Jan Gehl (Gehl, 1986, 2010, 2011; Gehl et al., 2006; Gehl & Svarre, 2013) has developed scholarship and methodological approaches that rely on systematic participant observation and surveys to determine what constitutes appropriate spaces that support vibrant residential life and liveable neighbourhoods. This paper makes the argument that these enquiries can be further complemented and informed by incorporating experiences from disciplines such as the geographies of architecture, particularly the research on ‘building events’ conducted by Lees and Baxter (Lees, 2001; Lees & Baxter, 2011), and Rose, Degen and Basdas (2010). Altogether, this can deepen the development of a more structured and evidence-based POE that is able to create and sustain learning loops that incorporate the inhabitants’ experience of spaces and shed light on the design process of housing schemes. The research question guiding the development of this paper is therefore: to what extent can the social value created by the design of housing blocks be better informed and conceptualised involving participant observation and architectural geography as part of post-occupancy evaluation?

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Keywords: architectural geography, housing design, post-occupancy evaluation, quality of life, social value

Roussou, E., & Charalambous, N. (2023, March). *On becoming a spatial agent: A comparative analysis of transdisciplinary design and build studio pedagogy in Cyprus and Sweden*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference* (pp. 37-40). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705327>

Abstract: As the traditional design studio becomes increasingly obsolete in the face of complex and multi-faceted realities, architectural education is in urgent need of profound restructuring (Awan et al., 2011; Doucet, 2017; Salazar Ferro et al., 2020). For several decades, the live studio framework, i.e. a framework that exposes students to the contingencies of a “real-world” experience, intertwined with a web of spatial, social, environmental and political aspects, has been challenging the archetype of the architect, allowing for a proliferation of the ways of being-in-context for students, educators, institutions and communities alike (Abrahams et al., 2021). There is, however, room for further

exploration in the ways in which the live studio is interpreted and implemented, within a rising post-capitalist wave of thought, both in the different geographical and cultural contexts, but also in its ideological standpoint and underpinnings.

The aim of this paper is to contribute to the ongoing discussion on reshaping live studio architectural education as a transformative pedagogy geared towards design activism, direct action and reclaiming learning as a commons that transcends the boundaries of academia (Bollier, 2021). More specifically, the study aims to provide insight on the impact of a transdisciplinary design & build pedagogical model on student perceptions regarding their positioning as future professionals, their attitude towards processes of cooperation and co-creation with various stakeholders, as well as their confidence levels regarding transdisciplinary, hands-on teamwork. A transnational comparative analysis of two courses, one at the University of Cyprus in Nicosia and the other at Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg, that share a focus on public space in suburban residential areas through similar learning objectives and syllabi, is used to both draw parallels and explore the differences between two distinct contexts, as well as highlight any transferable aspects and elements.

To address the above, the study draws on social sciences methodologies within a participatory action research (PAR) framework; a set of two questionnaires was handed out to the participating students of both courses, one in the beginning of each course and one at their completion, in order to trace and document both the collective and the individual shifts in mindsets and perceptions. Within the PAR framework, a reflexive insider researcher perspective methodology is used, solidified both by prior familiarity with these contexts in both a macro (cultural, historical) and a micro (educational, interpersonal) level, and by an active and immersed role as teachers throughout the process. This position enabled the enrichment of the research process by building bonds of trust between those involved, through which observation and in-depth analysis of formal (focus group session) and informal, everyday interactions was facilitated, while working collaboratively towards a common goal.

Building on the abovementioned, this paper reflects on the opportunities, implications as well as the limitations of a situated, transdisciplinary, design & build studio as a hub for training future architects in becoming socially conscious spatial agents, able to assess and respond effectively to complex challenges and work collectively towards a common future.

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Keywords: commons, design and build pedagogy, live studio, spatial agency, transdisciplinarity

Roussou, E., & Pappa, A. (2023, May). *From teaching the commons to commoning teaching: towards a reflexive architectural education.* In SMOOTH: Educational Commons and Active Social Inclusion Conference, Volos, Greece.

Abstract: While interest in the commons has increased over the years among academics in architecture, there are still limited examples of architectural education becoming in itself a commoning process. We suggest that in order to foster a commoning culture within architectural education, we need to invest in reflexive activities grounded on experimentation, creativity and collaboration.

This paper presents two academic activities independently developed but of similar characteristics in the number of the participants and their diversity in the level of study. The first is a thematic workshop held at the University Institute of Lisbon within an Erasmus+BIP, which through a scenario-based unstructured game invited students to strategize about their own urban commons developed in an empty plot at their university campus. The second case is the design & build workshop at the University of Cyprus implemented as the final stage of a semester-long co-creation process, in which students designed a park in suburban Nicosia and constructed part of its urban equipment.

Both cases lifted operational, architectural, political, financial and social aspects contributing to the reconsideration of the role of the architect and the design process. By reflecting on these experiences through students' and teachers' observations we aim to cross-pollinate between approaches and understand the contribution of commoning as a tool for knowledge production towards the development of social and operational skills of the future professionals.

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Keywords: commons

Tzika, Z., & Furman, S. (2023, March). Towards integrating social and environmental sustainability in housing: Conceptualisation, measurement frameworks, and indicators. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.)

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Abstract: The global housing crisis is an important social, environmental, and economic issue that is increasingly affecting more households, leading to housing deprivation. Housing is a “human right” (United Nations, 1948) and a primary physiological human need, underpinning progress towards improved quality of life, health, well-being, and life satisfaction. At the same time, the climate emergency demands more ecological ways of living that vastly reduce energy in order to achieve the European Commission’s goal of carbon neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, 2020). The current lack of adequate sustainable housing can be addressed by employing good practices throughout the design and construction of new housing, alongside drastic maintenance of existing buildings and neighbourhoods via regeneration, reuse and retrofit. The importance of involving communities in the decision-making process, by communicating lived experiences and realities, has been highlighted as a key factor to obtaining more equitable and socially just results (Dempsey et al., 2011). There is a demand for further empirical housing research to better understand the housing conditions of individuals and communities, subsequently improving the failings of housing.

This research explores the meaning of sustainability in housing, to better understand the potential to address current inequalities. Social and environmental sustainability were explored under a broadly constructivist and critical paradigm, not only to challenge their separation, but also to recast the entire relationship between them. Sustainability was first analysed as a theoretical concept, followed by its practical application. In the first part, a literature review was conducted concerning social and environmental sustainability in housing as stand-alone, and integrated concepts. In the second part, Sustainable Assessment Tools (SATs) and their associated indicators were analysed. Framework indicators and conceptual definitions identified within the literature were then compared. This analysis indicates that future investigation into the successes and failures of housing case studies should be conducted through an integrated approach to sustainability, to identify areas for improvement.

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Keywords: environmental sustainability, social sustainability, sustainable housing, sustainable measurement frameworks, Total Quality Assessment

Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023, June). *Understanding community participation in cooperative housing using the capabilities approach*. In *European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2023, Lodz, Poland*.

Abstract: As a response to the inadequate housing solutions provided by the housing markets, we observe the emergence of alternative initiatives and community-based approaches to housing provision. Such is the case in grant-of-use housing cooperative groups in Catalonia, which are either self-initiated or formed by secondary cooperatives or non-profit organisations. The democratic participation and organisation of the future residents are key elements of such housing initiatives, and they take place at different degrees at all stages of housing provision, from planning to construction, co-living, and maintenance. The processes vary as the motivations, visions, and needs set different priorities for each group. The capacity of each group to achieve their goals in terms of material and relational housing is being conditioned by their access to resources, their abilities, as well as different structural, operational and participant factors that constrain community participation. The aim of this paper is to understand the potential of community participation for different groups according to their varying resources and capabilities to promote more inclusive and equal processes. The participatory processes will be analysed using the capabilities approach. For that cooperative housing projects will be understood in relation to their resources (freedoms), opportunities (capabilities) of the groups and outcomes (functionings). The case of Catalonia will be used, using the data from the observatory of cooperative housing of Catalonia, as well as data from the fieldwork, observations and interviews. As a result, different participation typologies and consolidation processes have been identified. In that way, we can be aware of inequalities of access to resources, as well as deprivations of capacities and different profiles can be facilitated to have equal opportunities in co-creating their housing.

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Keywords: agency, built environment, case study, socio-spatial process

Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martinez, A. (2023). *Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia*. *Revista de Arquitectura*.

Abstract: The grant-of-use cooperative housing model that has emerged in Catalonia since 2015, has received interest as an alternative form of housing, originating from grassroots initiatives and placing the emphasis on community. Cooperative housing appears during periods when prevailing housing markets fail to provide adequate solutions. Groups are engaging in self-organisation, and collective decision-making, to assess their needs, negotiate resources, and co-create alternative housing options. While affordable housing access remains a core objective, cooperative housing goes beyond that, challenging individualistic living norms and emphasizing community relationships. This article examines the current state of cooperative housing in Catalonia, and explores its characteristics, through a comparative analysis of the existing cases, using graphs with the data from the Observatory of Cooperative Housing of Catalonia. The analysed attributes are categorised into five main areas: location, constitutive characteristics, the process of participation, economic characteristics, and communal living. Based on the analysis, it is observed that Catalonia's cooperative housing model has been evolving towards greater diversity, offering new possibilities for dwelling and fostering community-oriented housing. This evolution is evident in both the spatial characteristics of the houses and their social organisation. However, despite efforts from the cooperative housing groups and non-profit organisations in the sector to address challenges related to inclusion, long consolidation processes and financial barriers, there is still room for improvement.

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Abstract: Considering the complex meshing behind housing systems, the fact that housing policies are highly contextual is nothing ground-breaking. Variegated political and institutional pathways, economic conditions, the state of the housing stock, or simply socio-culturally constructed housing aspirations each singularly shape the ways housing systems function so as to—in an ideal world—provide decent homes for all. This complexity leads to a particular set of challenges for comparative housing researchers.

For example, anyone discussing 'social housing' across national boundaries needs to account for the wide variations in the meaning of the term, which may refer to very different objects in different countries (Scanlon et al., 2014). It could refer solely to publicly owned units offered as a last resort option for the most vulnerable (like in the United States), while it may also refer to a broad tenure type geared at a range of household types by a wide variety of actors, whether public, not for profit or collective (such as in Sweden or Singapore). In fact, even the previous sentences are oversimplifications, as only a—relatively—lengthy discussion of national specificities of different cases studied allows to create a space for comparison and differentiation (Haffner et al., 2009). In fact, defining and building understandings are a central piece of most comparative housing literature publications.

Yet, this relatively well acknowledged difficulty hides a wider conceptual issue; the words underpinning these definitions and differentiations tend to prevent leading researchers from making full sense of the various logics, institutions and actor behaviours operating within a specific housing system. In fact,

where the literature is quite explicit on the multiple variations across contexts and what they mean for comparative work. Indeed, there is little interest given to the actual learning process, how individual researchers acquire the knowledge necessary to carry research on housing, whether at home or abroad. Ultimately, this poses a challenge for comparative work, specifically: how can one effectively understand the national specificities of an ‘external’ housing system to an extent that would result in meaningful comparative work.

Stemming as a reflection on van Heur’s (2020) call to better integrate personal histories and the role of researchers positionality in affecting the knowledge they produce, this contribution will reflect both the personal and systemic aspects involved in the process of “learning” a new housing system. Especially when it comes to carrying comparative work involving policies, institutions, and actors.

The presentation will be articulated around the personal experience of the author in “learning” the French and Dutch housing system, as well as a comparison of the syllabus of housing courses from different universities in France, the Netherlands, Canada and Austria. Ultimately, it aims to underline in which ways the intersection between the initial perspective of the researcher as well as the specific idiosyncrasies of the researched system can allow to open new avenues. Similarly, it will also underline the difficulties involved in the process as well as possible shortcomings that can lead to issues, from cultural *faux pas* to incorrect inferences. Ultimately, this contribution aims to encourage housing researchers to reflect on the impact of their own frame of reference when engaging in comparative work.

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